

NOTES

Six-coordinate Thiosemicarbazone Complexes of some Bipositive Cations

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THE synthesis and characterisation of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-phenylthiosemicarbazone (NPTSZ) are reported here.

Experimental

Chemicals employed were of reagent grade. The tridentate thiosemicarbazone Schiff base (NPTSZ) was prepared by adding a solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (3.33 g in 20 ml ethanol) dropwise to a solution of phenylthiosemicarbazide (3.34 g in 20 ml ethanol) with continuous stirring. The mixture was refluxed in a water-bath for about 30 min and then allowed to cool to room temperature. The resulting yellow solid was washed with ethanol and dried over CaCl₂, (70%), m.p. 173° (Found: C, 67.17; H, 4.65; N, 13.04. C₁₈H₁₅N₃OS calcd. for: C, 67.28; H, 4.65; N, 13.08%); NPTSZ was found soluble in DMF.

The metal complexes were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities (0.002 mol) of the appropriate metal acetate hydrate (in 50 ml hot DMF) and NPTSZ (in 50 ml hot DMF) on a sand-bath for 2–4 h. The resulting coloured solids were washed with hot DMF and dried. The complexes were powdery, air-stable and insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, benzene, DMF and DMSO.

Results and Discussions

The analytical data (Table 1) of the complexes agree with the general formula (ML₂.2H₂O), where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} and H₂L = C₁₈H₁₅N₃OS = NPTSZ. The ir spectra of NPTSZ show the presence of strong bands at 3 150 (NH) and 3 390 cm⁻¹ (OH phenolic). Three bands due to N–C=S modes are observed at 1 515, 1 265 and 940 cm⁻¹. Some new bands in the regions 1 655–1 650 (C=N–N), 1 600 (C=N–N=C) and 670–665 cm⁻¹

(C–S, due to replacement of N–C=S into N=C–S) are observed. The ir spectra of the complexes contain NH band of the free ligand suggesting that NH is not involved in complexation. The positive shift by 2–8 cm⁻¹ of ν_{C–O} band at 1 540, deformation of phenolic OH at 1 280 cm⁻¹ and disappearance of OH frequencies in the complexes collectively suggests the involvement of phenolic OH in complexation. The lowering of ν_{C–N} band of the free ligand by ~15 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes indicates participation of azomethine nitrogen in coordination³. The presence of phenolic oxygen bridge seems to be unlikely as no positive shift of ν_{C–O} band is observed⁴. However a sulphur-bridged dimeric arrangement may be tentatively assigned for the complexes. This is supported by their insolubility in non-polar solvents⁵, presence

of M $\begin{matrix} \diagup \\ \text{S} \\ \diagdown \end{matrix}$ M band (460 cm⁻¹) and low magnetic moments (Table 1). The other non-ligand bands due to ν_{M–O} and ν_{M–N} and ν_{M–S}⁴ in the metal sensitive regions are also located. The appearance of ν_{M–O}, ν_{C–N} and ν_{M–S} in the ir spectra of the complexes indicates that thiosemicarbazone Schiff base is coordinated to the metal(II) ion via the phenolic oxygen, and azomethine nitrogen and sulphur atom.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF NPTSZ COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ _{eff} B.M.
		Metal	N	
Co(L) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Green	14.09 (14.28)	10.03 (10.14)	3.51
Ni(L) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Reddish yellow	13.58 (14.27)	10.12 (10.18)	2.74
Cu(L) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Reddish brown	15.01 (15.07)	10.01 (10.04)	1.41

*L = C₁₈H₁₅N₃OS²⁻

The presence of water molecule within the coordination sphere is supported by the appearance of bands in the regions 3 600–3 500, 1 655–1 650 and 950–900 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes attributable to OH stretching, HOH deformation and H₂O rocking modes respectively^{6,7}. In the TG analysis, the percentage weight-loss observed at 220–280° corresponds to the elimination of two water molecules thus supporting the presence of coordinated water. The complexes decompose in the range 220–340° and the order of thermal stability is Ni^{II} ≈ Co^{II} > Cu^{II}.

All the complexes are paramagnetic and have low magnetic moments presumably due to antiferromagnetic interactions between a pair of metal(II)

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ions⁹. The various ligand field parameters, viz. ν_2/ν_1 , $10Dq$, β' , β , β^0 were calculated⁹ and found to be 2.12, 7.61, 1.25 (σ_1/σ_2); 11 780, 10 000, 12 781 cm^{-1} ; 947, 826; 0.975, 0.783 and 2.47, 21.69% for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively. All these spectral data and the band positions fit in the range of octahedral complexes, giving tacit support to this geometry.

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Complexes of Bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-aminopyridine with Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury-(II)

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METAL complexes of various Schiff bases derived from 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (vanillin) have been studied^{1,2}. In continuation of our earlier studies³ Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with vanillin-2-aminopyridine (HMBAP) are reported.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

The Schiff base ligand, HMBP (L) was not isolated in solid state³, because on mixing vanillin with 2-aminopyridine the solid was converted to liquid. So, for the preparation of the complexes *in situ* method was adopted.

Preparation of complexes: To an ethanolic solution of vanillin was added an alcoholic solution

of metal halides with constant stirring. To this solution, an ethanolic solution of 2-aminopyridine was added and the solution was refluxed for 1 h on a water-bath. The resulting crystals separated out on cooling were filtered, washed with alcohol and ether and dried under reduced pressure. In all the complexes the metal halides (MX), vanillin and 2-aminopyridine ratio was 1 : 2 : 2. Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} form complexes of the type $[\text{ML}_2\text{X}_2]$, whereas Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} form complexes of the type $[\text{ML}_2]\text{X}_2$.

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 4000A spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a EM 390 spectrometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by a Gouy balance and molar conductance on a Systronics 303 conductivity bridge. The analytical and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Low molar conductance values (20–24 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes measured in DMF at 25° at a concentration of $10^{-3}M$ suggest that complexes are non-electrolytes⁴. Molar conductivity values (110–122 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of the Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes indicate their electrolytic nature⁵. The electrolytic behaviour of the complexes implies that the anions are present outside the coordination sphere. The ir spectra of the free ligand show bands at 1 630 ($\text{CH}=\text{N}$)⁶ and 1 540 cm^{-1} (pyridine ring)⁷; in the complexes of the type $[\text{ML}_2\text{X}_2]$ and $[\text{ML}_2]\text{X}_2$, there is a negative shift in both the frequencies by nearly 30 and 45 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen and pyridine nitrogen⁸. The ring stretching vibrations are due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ observed in the region 1 540–1 330 cm^{-1} . The appearance of a new band in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes at 270–280 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{X}}$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ and I).

The ir spectra of the nitrate complexes show bands at ~1 450, ~1 225, ~1 000 and ~950 cm^{-1} , whereas the perchlorate complexes show bands at ~1 270, ~1 130 and ~970 cm^{-1} . These bands unambiguously suggest the presence of coordinated nitrate⁹ and perchlorate¹⁰ anions. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes in DMF supports the presence of the anions in the coordination sphere. The magnetic moment values of complexes are included in Table 1.

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes exhibit bands at 9 000, 19 000 and 24 000 cm^{-1} , corresponding to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_2), and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_3). The crystal field parameters ν_3/ν_1 , Dq/B , B , $10Dq$ and β were found to be 2.13, 1.16, 791.66 cm^{-1} , 9175.6 cm^{-1} and 0.70 respectively. The lowering in the value of B (29.31%) from the free-ion value for Co^{II} (1 120 cm^{-1}) suggests covalent nature of bonding. These values are in close accordance